

THE CONCEPT AND STRUCTURE OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Teshaboyev A.Yu.

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages, Head of the Department of Social Humanities, Pedagogy and Psychology. Koychiyev.G'.G is a student of the Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10113155>

The article reveals opinions about the national program, education system, humanitarianism, freedom, values, people, pre-school education, modern vocational education system. Knowledge of education is also mentioned.

Keywords: education, freedom, value, person, person, profession, school, knowledge

Today, every developed country has an established and stable educational system aimed at meeting the needs of the state, society and the individual. The operation of this system is regulated by legislation. The educational system is a set of educational institutions of various levels that ensure the continuous education of a person.

The national curriculum education system is a set of interacting systems:

- continuous education programs and state education standards of various levels and directions;
- branches of educational institutions that implement them, regardless of their organizational and legal forms, types and types;
- educational management bodies and institutions and organizations subordinate to them.

The activity of the national curriculum education system is determined by the following principles:

1. Humanistic character of education, priority of universal values, human life and health, free development of the individual. Citizenship, diligence, respect for human rights and freedoms, education of feelings of love for the environment, Motherland, and family.
2. Unity of the federal cultural and educational space. Protection and development of the educational system of national cultures, regional cultural traditions and characteristics in a multi-ethnic state.
3. Openness of education to the public, adaptation of the education system to the levels and features of development and training of students and students.
4. Secular nature of education in state and city educational institutions.
5. Freedom and pluralism in education.
6. Democratic, state-public nature of educational management, autonomy of educational institutions.

The content of Russian education is determined by two types of educational programs: general education (basic and additional) and professional (basic and additional). General education programs are aimed at solving the problems of forming the general culture of the Person, adapting the Person to the life of the society, creating a foundation for the conscious choice and mastering of professional education programs. These include pre-school education, primary general education, basic general education and secondary (full) general

education programs. Vocational education programs are aimed at solving the problems of consistently improving the level of professional and general education, training specialists with appropriate qualifications. Vocational programs include primary vocational education, secondary vocational education, tertiary and post-university educational programs. The minimum educational content of each program is determined by the relevant state standard. They are implemented through the following network of educational institutions:

- preschool education: kindergartens, kindergartens, children's centers;
- general education (primary general, basic general, secondary (full) general education): schools, gymnasiums, lyceums;
- vocational education (primary, secondary, higher): schools, colleges, technical schools, universities;
- special (remedial) schools for children with developmental disabilities: schools for the visually impaired, deaf and others;
- additional educational institutions: music, sports, art schools, youth creative centers, etc.;
- institutions for orphans and children left without parental care: orphanages, boarding schools;
- other educational institutions.

Preschool educational institutions are established to educate children from one to six years of age, to protect and strengthen their physical and mental health, to develop individual abilities and to correct developmental deficiencies. They are open to help the family, because the child's first and main teachers are his parents. The main types of preschool educational institutions are kindergarten, kindergarten, gymnasium, child development center. Methodological, diagnostic and advisory support organized by local state authorities should be provided to families where children of preschool age are raised at home.

The activity of preschool educational institutions is regulated by the model regulation "On preschool educational institutions". According to this document, the tasks of educational institutions include protection of children's life and health, their intellectual and physical development, familiarization with universal human values, and interaction with the family in the interests of the child's comprehensive development. In the conditions of the modern open educational space, preschool educational institutions are free to choose a specific direction of the educational process, educational programs and methods. Based on this, there are different types of kindergartens in Russian practice. For example, the compensatory kindergarten, which focuses on correcting deviations in the physical and mental development of the child, or the development, which focuses on the intellectual, artistic or physical development of the child, has been reformed with the emergence of alternative pedagogical and psychological technologies.

It should be noted that almost the entire network of existing preschool educational institutions was created in the past, which provided children with care, nutrition, medical care, education and upbringing. At the moment, due to the deterioration of the material and technical base and insufficient financing by the public sector, the number of kindergartens and the number of services provided are decreasing. Current problems of the state are the

problem of maintaining the network of preschool educational institutions, the problem of continuity of preschool and primary school education.

The school is designed for a harmonious entry into the educational activities of the child. The tasks of primary school teachers include the development of the child's motivation, ability and desire to learn. In primary school, students receive basic education: they learn to count, read, write, and acquire elements of theoretical thinking, cultural speech, and behavior. Educational subjects in primary school are integrated and are aimed at forming the child's initial ideas about nature, society, man and his work. In addition, music, work, physical and aesthetic education classes are held for students in the curriculum.

The main school is aimed at creating a solid foundation for preparing students for general education and involving them in the life of society. The foundation school is designed to ensure the Personality of students, their individual inclinations and abilities, life and professional self-determination. At this stage of education, the scientific view of the world and the individual's outlook are formed. In addition to compulsory subjects, the curriculum of the main school includes optional lessons aimed at developing the interests of students.

Basic school is compulsory. Its graduates have the right to choose: to continue their studies in high school or to continue their studies in vocational schools.

The general education school ensures completion of general educational preparation of students on the basis of wide and deep differentiation and creates optimal psychological and pedagogical conditions for students' professional and life self-determination.

For children with developmental disabilities, special educational institutions (classes, groups) with a corrective character aimed at their treatment, education and training, and social adjustment are established. Children are sent to such specific educational institutions by the educational authorities with the consent of the parents or their substitutes according to the conclusion of the psychological-medical-pedagogical consultation.

Medical and social rehabilitation, education and vocational training for teenagers who are socially dangerous, have deviant behavior, need special conditions of education and upbringing and require a special pedagogical approach there are special educational institutions for Such educational institutions accept children over the age of eleven. A teenager can be sent there for education only by a court decision.

Based on the right to education guaranteed by the state, conditions are created for citizens to receive basic general and primary vocational education in educational-labor and correctional-labor institutions.

Vocational education institutions are opened to implement vocational education programs of primary, secondary and higher vocational education.

Primary vocational education is aimed at training skilled workers in all the main directions of socially useful activities on the basis of basic general education. Vocational schools are the main type of educational institution implementing the primary vocational education program.

Secondary vocational education is a secondary vocational education aimed at meeting the needs of a person to deepen and expand their education on the basis of basic general, secondary (full) general or primary vocational education. aimed at training wheat

specialists. It can be obtained at secondary vocational educational institutions (technical schools, schools, colleges) or at the first stage of higher vocational educational institutions.

Higher professional education consists of meeting the needs of the Person to deepen and expand education on the basis of secondary (full) general and secondary vocational education, training and retraining of specialists of the appropriate level. It can be obtained in higher professional educational institutions (institutes, universities, academies). Individuals with primary or secondary vocational education in the relevant profile can receive higher vocational education in shortened accelerated programs.

One of the important features of the modern education system is legalized organizational and legal forms of educational institutions (state, municipal, non-state), forms of education (full-time, part-time, part-time, family, external, distance education), educational content and organizing the pedagogical process in the educational institution. The modern education system is moving away from the previous unification and standardization.

Most importantly, today the field of education has begun to acquire the characteristics of one of the few social fields where the interests of the state, society and the individual actually collide. In addition, taking into account the federal nature of the state structure, the approach to solving problems in the field of education also reveals the interests of the regional order, which is determined by the specific characteristics of the educational complex and its intellectual potential.

References:

- 1.Mirziyoyev SH.M. Tanqidiy tahlil, qat'iy tartib-intizom va Shaxsiy javobgarlik-har bir rahbar faoliyatining kundalik qoidasi bo'lishi kerakToshkent: O'zbekiston, 20017
- 2.Mirziyoyev SH.M. Erkin va farovon, demokratik O'zbekiston davlitini birgalikda barpo etamiz. -Toshkent:O'zbekiston, 2016
- 3.Mirziyoyev SH.M. Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va oliyjanob halqimiz bilan birga qo'ramiz. – Toshkent O'zbekiston, 2017
- 4.Mirziyoyev SH.M. Qonun ustuvorligi va inson manfaatlarini ta'minlash - yurt taraqqiyoiti va xalq farovonligining garovi.-Toshkent:o'zbekiston, 2017
- 5.Golovanova N.F. Pedagogika. 2018. <https://studme.org/297874/>
- 6.Jo'raev R. H. va boshqalar. Pedagogika fani konsepsiyasi. -Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2014.-232 b. 260
- 7.Umarovich M. M. THE IMPORTANCE OF COOPERATION BETWEEN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND FAMILIES ON THE BASIS OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS IN THE FORMATION OF YOUTH SPIRITUALITY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 4. – C. 157-163.
- 8.Mamadaliyev Muzaffar Umarovich. (2022). IN FORMING THE SPIRIT OF YOUTH PHILOSOPHICAL WORLDWIDE AND THE SCIENTIFIC SIGNIFICANCE OF OUR NATIONAL SPIRITUAL HERITAGE. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(4), 338–342. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SKJ6E>
- 9.Тешабоев А.Ю., Умнова М.К. МИРОВОЙ ОПЫТ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ РАБОТНИКОВ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ // Вестник науки и образования. 2021.

№16-2 (119). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/mirovoy-opyt-povysheniya-kvalifikatsii-rabotnikov-doshkolnogo-obrazovaniya>

10.Алиева Р. А., Усманов У., Алиева Ф. АНАЛИЗ РИСКОВ ДЛЯ ЗДОРОВЬЯ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МОБИЛЬНЫХ ТЕЛЕФОНОВ // "GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS. – 2023. – Т. 9. – №. 1.

